

Supplemental Material for:

The epileptic network of Lennox-Gastaut syndrome: cortically driven and reproducible across age

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Supplemental table 1: Demographic and electroclinical characteristics of patients with LGS. Each row contains information for one patient. Each patient is assigned a unique identity (ID) number. ID numbers 1-10 indicate patients in the pediatric group, and ID numbers 11-25 indicate patients in the older group. *Abbreviations:* AA = atypical absence; AEDs = anti-epileptic drugs; CI = cognitive impairment; F = female; FIAS = focal impaired awareness seizure; GPFA = generalized paroxysmal fast activity; GTCS = generalized tonic-clonic seizure; HHV-6 = human herpes virus type 6; HSV-1 = herpes simplex virus type 1; IQ = intelligence quotient; L = left; M = male; R = right; SSW = slow spike-and-wave.

AED abbreviations: CBZ = carbamazepine; CLB = clobazam; CZP = clonazepam; ESM = ethosuximide; FBM = felbamate; LCM = lacosamide; LEV = levetiracetam; LTG = lamotrigine; OXC = oxcarbazepine; PHT = phenytoin; STM = sulthiame; VPA = sodium valproate; TGB = tiagabine; TPM = topiramate; ZNS = zonisamide.

ID	Age at study, yrs	Age at seizure onset, yrs	Sex	AEDs at time of study	Seizure types	Interictal EEG features	Structural MRI findings	Suspected etiology	Cognitive features
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Pediatric group (n=10)

1	5	0	M	TPM, VPA	Tonic, AA, myoclonic	SSW, GPFA	Bilateral occipital ulegyria	Neonatal hypoglycemia	Severe CI Nonverbal
2	4	0.2	F	CZP, LTG, VPA, ZNS	Tonic, spasms	SSW, GPFA	Unremarkable	ALG13 mutation	Severe CI Nonverbal
3	15	0.3	M	CBZ, LEV, ZNS	Tonic, AA, spasms	SSW, GPFA, L temporal and L frontal discharges	Unremarkable	Unknown	Moderate CI Minimally verbal
4	13	0.4	F	CLB, TPM, LTG, VPA	Tonic, AA, spasms	SSW, GPFA, multi-focal discharges	Cerebellar atrophy (incidental)	Unknown	Severe CI Nonverbal
5	11	0.8	F	CLB, TPM	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, multi-focal discharges	Encephalomalacia and gliosis involving insula, perisylvian, and prerolandic regions	HSV-1 encephalitis	Severe CI Nonverbal
6	10	0.8	F	CZP, LTG, TPM, VPA	Tonic	SSW, GPFA	R medial temporal dysembryoplastic neuroepithelial tumour	Dysembryoplastic neuroepithelial tumour on the background of a chromosomal abnormality (partial monosomy 18p)	Severe CI Nonverbal
7	2	1	M	CLB, LEV, LTG, VPA	Tonic, atonic, FIAS, GTCS	SSW, GPFA	L temporal dysplasia	Malformation of cortical development	Severe CI Nonverbal
8	10	2	F	CZP, TPM, VPA	Tonic, atonic, AA, spasms	SSW, GPFA	Bilateral hippocampal sclerosis	HHV-6 encephalitis	Severe CI Nonverbal
9	6	3	M	CLB, LCM, LTG, VPA	Tonic, atonic, myoclonic	SSW, GPFA	Bilateral hippocampal sclerosis	HHV-6 encephalitis	Severe CI Nonverbal

10	13	12	F	ESM, LTG, VPA	Tonic, AA, myoclonic, GTCS	SSW, GPFA	Unremarkable	Unknown	Severe CI Nonverbal
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Older group (n=15)

11	32	0.25	F	LTG, VPA	Tonic, AA, GTCS, FIAS	SSW, GPFA, R posterior and R temporal discharges	L frontal gliosis, previous R parietal corticectomy, R parietal gliosis near resection margin	Infantile bacterial meningitis (salmonella)	Mild CI Full-scale IQ =70
12	25	0.5	M	CBZ, LEV, TPM, VPA	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA	Tuberous sclerosis, multiple lesions	Tuberous sclerosis complex	Severe CI Non-verbal
13	36	3	F	CLB, LTG, PHT, VPA	Tonic, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, L frontal discharges	Unremarkable with previous L anterior temporal lobectomy and anterior corpus callosotomy	Unknown	Moderate CI Lives in supported accommodation
14	37	4	M	CBZ, LEV, TGB	Tonic, AA, FIAS	SSW, GPFA, R temporal and R parietal discharges	R temporal cortical loss and gliosis	Perinatal infarction	Mild CI Impairment in verbal memory
15	33	4	F	CBZ, LEV, LTG, VPA	Tonic, AA, GTCS, FIAS	SSW, GPFA, bifrontal discharges	Bilateral parietal double cortex	<i>LIS1</i> c.484G>A (p.Gly162Ser) mutation with malformation of cortical development	Moderate CI Full-scale IQ = 60
16	40	5	F	CLB, LTG, VPA	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA	Complex L parietal dysplasia	Malformation of cortical development	Moderate CI
17	42	7	M	CBZ, CLB, LEV, TGB, VPA	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA	R frontal transmantle dysplasia	Malformation of cortical development	Severe CI Lives in supported accommodation
18	10	7	M	CLB, ESM, TPM	Tonic, AA, spasms, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, multifocal discharges	Unusual L temporal sulcation (incidental)	Unknown	Severe CI Minimally verbal Full-scale IQ = 42
19	25	7	F	CBZ, CLB, LTG, STM	Tonic, AA, FIAS	SSW, GPFA, L frontal and L occipital discharges	Unremarkable	Infantile bacterial meningitis	Moderate CI
20	38	8	M	LEV, LTG, TPM, VPA	Tonic, FIAS, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, L frontal discharges	L frontal dysplasia	Malformation of cortical development	Mild CI Impairment in working memory, verbal fluency, psychomotor speed
21	16	9	F	CLB, LEV, STM	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, R frontotemporal discharges	Unremarkable	Unknown	Mild CI Full-scale IQ = 70-80
22	38	10	F	LEV, LTG, OXC	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, R temporal and bifrontal discharges	Unremarkable	Unknown	Mild CI Impairment in verbal recall, visuospatial processing
23	40	13	M	CBZ, CLB, FBM, TPM	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA	Unremarkable with previous anterior corpus callosotomy	Unknown	Mild CI
24	19	13	M	LTG, OXC, PHT, VPA	Tonic, AA, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, bifrontal discharges	Unremarkable	Chromosome 15q11.2-q13.1 inversion-duplication	Moderate CI Verbal IQ = 73 Performance IQ = 50
25	44	28	F	CLB, LTG, OXC, PHB, TPM	Tonic, FIAS, GTCS	SSW, GPFA, R temporoparietal discharges, L frontotemporal discharges	Unremarkable	Unknown	Mild CI Impairment in attention, working memory, processing speed. Obsessional behavior.

Supplemental table 2: Patient-specific voxel coordinates and peak *F*-scores for regions-of-interest (ROIs) used in the dynamic causal modeling (DCM) analysis. Each row contains information for one patient (each patient is assigned a unique identity [ID] number; ID numbers match those used in supplemental table 1 above). ID numbers 1-10 indicate patients in the pediatric group, and ID numbers 11-25 indicate patients in the older group. For each patient, the center voxel coordinates (*x*, *y*, and *z* positions [mm] in Montreal Neurological Institute space) are provided for each of three spherical ROIs (radius=5 mm) used in the DCM analysis (i.e., cortex/middle frontal gyrus [MFG], thalamus, and brainstem). The center coordinates of each ROI were defined by the position of the voxel with peak *F*-score resulting from the patient's individual-level EEG-fMRI analysis. For further details, refer to Methods in the manuscript. *this patient was excluded from all DCM analyses because they did not show significant individual-level EEG-fMRI involvement of the brainstem ($p>0.01$).

ID	Cortical (MFG) ROI coordinates (peak <i>F</i> -score)	Thalamic ROI coordinates (peak <i>F</i> -score)	Brainstem ROI coordinates (peak <i>F</i> -score)
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Pediatric group (n=10)

1*	50, 22, 36 (<i>F</i> =2.82)	-12, -16, 12 (<i>F</i> =2.93)	-6, -22, -24 (<i>F</i> =1.67)
2	48, 10, 44 (<i>F</i> =16.76)	8, -14, 14 (<i>F</i> =5.12)	2, -20, -24 (<i>F</i> =9.83)
3	44, 24, 40 (<i>F</i> =18.56)	6, -16, 12 (<i>F</i> =5.5)	-2, -24, -22 (<i>F</i> =8.1)
4	46, 26, 26 (<i>F</i> =25.53)	10, -8, 8 (<i>F</i> =9.85)	8, -26, -22 (<i>F</i> =6.1)
5	32, 12, 56 (<i>F</i> =3.83)	8, -12, 4 (<i>F</i> =6.92)	4, -28, -22 (<i>F</i> =4.97)
6	28, 30, 40 (<i>F</i> =22.23)	-6, -12, 4 (<i>F</i> =9.96)	0, -20, -24 (<i>F</i> =8.96)
7	-42, 34, 28 (<i>F</i> =18.36)	6, -10, 2 (<i>F</i> =7.96)	-8, -28, -22 (<i>F</i> =9.27)
8	-40, 8, 56 (<i>F</i> =27.59)	-4, -8, 6 (<i>F</i> =21.97)	12, -26, -24 (<i>F</i> =8.35)
9	-46, 10, 46 (<i>F</i> =72.49)	6, -10, 12 (<i>F</i> =57.25)	10, -30, -28 (<i>F</i> =19.11)
10	-48, 26, 28 (<i>F</i> =7.2)	8, -20, 4 (<i>F</i> =8.87)	4, -30, -26 (<i>F</i> =4.66)

Older group (n=15)

11	48, 14, 36 (<i>F</i> =11.16)	8, -6, 10 (<i>F</i> =6.17)	2, -34, -40 (<i>F</i> =5.8)
12	48, 14, 36 (<i>F</i> =48.82)	8, -6, 10 (<i>F</i> =31.66)	4, -30, -16 (<i>F</i> =14.14)
13	-40, 12, 42 (18.28)	-6, -10, 12 (<i>F</i> =8.08)	-2, -30, -24 (<i>F</i> =7.31)

14	-38, 18, 30 ($F=16.45$)	6, -6, 8 ($F=6.71$)	0, -26, -24 ($F=5.25$)
15	44, 12, 52 ($F=45.7$)	-10, -28, 10 ($F=11.93$)	0, -32, -16 ($F=6.79$)
16	36, 10, 60 ($F=10.76$)	-8, -6, 10 ($F=9.29$)	-6, -34, -28 ($F=5.76$)
17	-46, 12, 34 ($F=27.37$)	-6, -18, 8 ($F=35.98$)	0, -30, -32 ($F=22.39$)
18	-44, 6, 52 ($F=17.28$)	-8, -24, 10 ($F=17.96$)	8, -34, -28 ($F=11.12$)
19	-40, 14, 32 ($F=19.35$)	10, -6, 12 ($F=17.87$)	16, -30, -36 ($F=13.7$)
20	42, 30, 32 ($F=4.85$)	16, -22, 14 ($F=4.93$)	12, -24, -32 ($F=6.23$)
21	-50, 20, 32 ($F=82.12$)	6, -16, 12 ($F=32.71$)	-6, -26, -32 ($F=58.37$)
22	-42, 4, 54 ($F=20.03$)	10, -26, 10 ($F=7.89$)	2, -26, -26 ($F=5.8$)
23	-36, 0, 60 ($F=13.4$)	6, -6, 8 ($F=8.92$)	2, -34, -42 ($F=6.32$)
24	-42, 22, 38 ($F=21.49$)	-6, -20, 12 ($F=13.24$)	0, -26, -24 ($F=13.27$)
25	48, 18, 44 ($F=63.45$)	8, -6, 10 ($F=42.28$)	10, -34, -32 ($F=10.2$)